

Synthesis, Characterization and *In Vitro* Antimicrobial Screening of Some Pyrazolylpyridyl Substituted Dicoumarins

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ABSTRACT

In the present study, a series of pyrazolyl pyridyl substituted dicoumarins has been synthesized. The synthesis of various 3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-3'''-yl)-1*H*-pyrazol-4'''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarins and 3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-4'''-yl)-1*H*-pyrazol-4'''-yl) pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarins has been carried out by the reaction of various 3-coumarinoyl methyl pyridinium bromide salts with 3-(3-(1-phenyl-3-(pyridin-3-yl)-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)acryloyl)coumarins and 3-(3-(1-phenyl-3-(pyridin-4-yl)-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)acryloyl)coumarins (coumarin chalcones) respectively under *Krohnke's* reaction condition. Structural assignments were based on spectroscopic methods (IR, ¹H-NMR, ¹³C-APT, Mass spectral data and elemental analysis). The compounds were subjected to *in vitro* antimicrobial screening against representative panel of bacteria (*Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhi*) and fungi (*Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*).

Keywords: Coumarins, dicoumarins, krohnke synthesis, antimicrobial screening, broth dilution method, spectral data.

INTRODUCTION

Coumarins (2*H*-1-benzopyran-2-ones) are well known aromatic δ -lactones isolated from variety of plant sources¹. Coumarins have a wide range of applications in the field of pharmaceuticals due to their diverse pharmacological and biological properties such as antimicrobial², anticoagulant³, antitumor⁴, anti-inflammatory⁵, anti-HIV⁶, anticonvulsant⁷, antidiabetic⁸, analgesic⁹, antianxiety¹⁰ etc. A wide number of coumarin derivatives have been found in

literature which contain nucleus like pyridine, indole, imidazole, diazole, thiazole, and triazole etc. as a substituent group possess important biological activities¹¹⁻¹⁵.

Among variety of heterocyclic substituted coumarins, pyridyl substituted coumarins draw a special attention in synthetic as well as medicinal field due to their diverse pharmacological activities. A number of coumarin derivatives having pyridine substitution mainly at 3- or 4- position of the coumarin, possess various biological properties viz antifungal¹⁶, anticoagulant¹⁷, antihyperglycemic¹⁸, CNS depressant activity¹⁹ and also shown electrochemical and photophysical properties²⁰.

In literature pyrazolyl substituted pyridine derivatives are well documented and reported to possess several medicinal properties like antimicrobial activity²¹, cytotoxic activity, DNA binding property²², anticancer activity²³, used as a potent inhibitor of the transforming growth factor- β type I receptor kinase domain²⁴ and exhibited appreciable cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) potency and selectivity²⁵. They also showed some photo-physical and electrochemiluminescence properties²⁶.

In dicoumarinyl pyridines, the pyridine nucleus is flanked between two coumarin moieties at C-2 and C-6 position and the structure seems as if two coumarins have 3-(2-pyridyl) substitution. We had earlier synthesized various dicoumarinyl pyridines in our laboratory by using well-known *Krohnke's* pyridine synthesis²⁷⁻²⁸. Thus considering the importance of pyridylcoumarins, pyrazolyl substituted pyridines and

in continuation of our synthesis work on dicoumarinyl pyridines, we have synthesized some new pyrazolylpyridyl substituted dicoumarins in present work.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the melting points are uncorrected. All reactions were performed with commercially available reagents and they were used without further purification. Organic solvents were purified by standard methods and stored over molecular sieves. All the IR spectra (KBr disc) were recorded on Shimadzu FTIR 8400-S spectrometer. ¹H-NMR and ¹³C-APT spectra were recorded on Bruker Advance 400 spectrometer operating at 400 MHz for ¹H-NMR and 100 MHz for ¹³C-APT. The chemical shift (δ) is reported in ppm using chloroform-d as a solvent and calibrated standard solvent signal. Mass spectra were recorded on Shimadzu QP 2010 spectrometer. Elemental analysis was carried out on Perkin-Elmer 2400 C-H-N-S-O Analyser Series-II. All the compounds were routinely checked for completion of the reaction on silica gel 60 F254 TLC plates and their spots were visualized by exposure to a UV lamp, iodine vapour or KMnO₄ reagents. In the present work, the synthesis of various 3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-3''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarins (**6a-i**) and 3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-4''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarins (**7a-i**) has been carried out by reacting appropriate 3-coumarinoyl methyl pyridinium bromide salt (**3a-c**) with various coumarin chalcones 3-(3-(1-phenyl-3-(pyridin-3-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)acryloyl)coumarins (**4a-c**) and 3-(3-(1-phenyl-3-(pyridin-4-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)acryloyl)coumarins (**5a-c**) respectively in the presence of ammonium acetate in refluxing acetic acid. Compounds (**3a-c**) were prepared according to literature procedure^{29,30,31}.

1) General procedure for the preparation of 3-(3-(1-phenyl-3-(pyridin-3-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)acryloyl)coumarins (**4a-c**) and 3-(3-(1-phenyl-3-(pyridin-4-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)acryloyl)coumarins (**5a-c**):

In a 100 mL round bottom flask, an appropriate 3-acetyl coumarin (0.01 mol) and appropriate pyrazole

aldehyde (0.015 mol) were taken in 50 mL of ethanol. Catalytic amount of piperidine (1.0 mL) was added

and the reaction mixture was stirred for 10 minutes at room temperature. The mixture was then refluxed on water bath for 4 hours. It was allowed to cool to room temperature. A solid product separated out was filtered off, washed with cold ethanol and dried. It was recrystallized from ethanol. Chalcones **4a**, **4b**, **5a** and **5b** were prepared according to literature procedure³².

2) General procedure for the synthesis of Synthesis of 3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-3''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarins (**6a-i**) and 3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-4''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarins (**7a-i**).

In a 100 mL round bottom flask equipped with a condenser, guard tube and magnetic needle, an appropriate 3-coumarinoyl methyl pyridinium bromide salt (**3a-c**) (0.003 mol) was taken in glacial acetic acid (15 mL). To this, ammonium acetate (0.03 mol) was added with stirring at room temperature. Then a solution of appropriate 3-(3-(1-phenyl-3-(pyridin-3-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)acryloyl)coumarin (**4a-c**) or 3-(3-(1-phenyl-3-(pyridin-4-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)acryloyl)coumarin (**5a-c**) (0.003 mol) in acetic acid (15 mL) was added with stirring at room temperature and reaction mixture was further stirred for 45 minutes and then refluxed for 8 hours at 140°C. It was then allowed to come to room temperature. The reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water (75 mL). A crude solid obtained was extracted with chloroform (3 x 30 mL). The combined chloroform extract was washed with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution (3 x 20 mL), with water (3 x 20 mL) and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The removal of chloroform under vacuum gave a solid product. This was purified by column chromatography using silica gel and chloroform-pet. ether (60-80) (8:2) as an eluent to give product (**6a-i**) and (**7a-i**). The compounds were recrystallized from chloroform-hexane.

Where,
 4a=5a: R₂=R₃=H
 4b=5b: R₂=OCH₃, R₃=H
 4c=5c: R₂=H, R₃=Br

Where,
 3a : R= R₁= H
 3b : R= OCH₃, R₁= H
 3c : R= H, R₁= Br

Scheme 1. Synthetic pathway for the synthesis of target compounds (**6a-i**) and (**7a-i**)

Compounds	R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
6a : 7a	H	H	H	H
6b : 7b	H	H	OCH ₃	H
6c : 7c	H	H	H	Br
6d : 7d	OCH ₃	H	H	H
6e : 7e	OCH ₃	H	OCH ₃	H
6f : 7f	OCH ₃	H	H	Br
6g : 7g	H	Br	H	H
6h : 7h	H	Br	OCH ₃	H
6i : 7i	H	Br	H	Br

Spectral Interpretation

6-Bromo-3-(3-(1-phenyl-3-(pyridin-3-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)acryloyl)coumarins (4c): IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}): 1728 (C=O stretching of δ -lactone of coumarin), 1684 (α, β unsaturated carbonyl group), 1605 and 1543 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 756 (C-H bending vibration of mono substituted benzene ring), 3047 (aromatic C-H stretching). ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 7.41-8.99 (16H, multiplet, thirteen aromatic protons + C₄proton of coumarin + two olefinic protons).

6-Bromo-3-(3-(1-phenyl-3-(pyridin-4-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)acryloyl)coumarins (5c): IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}): 1728 (C=O stretching of δ -lactone of coumarin), 1674 (α, β unsaturated carbonyl group), 1605 and 1543 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 764 (C-H bending vibration of mono substituted benzene ring), 3047 (aromatic C-H stretching). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 7.29-8.99 (16H, multiplet, thirteen aromatic protons + C₄ proton of coumarin + two olefinic protons).

3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-3''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarin (6a): Yield: 71%, m.p. 250-252°C., IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}): 1726 (C=O stretching of δ -lactone of coumarin), 1608 and 1457 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 691 and 759 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 3062 (aromatic C-H stretching). ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 7.35-8.08 (15H, multiplet, Ar-H except C_{5'''}-H, C₃-H, C₅-H, C_{6'''}-H, C_{4'}-H, C_{4''}-H and C_{2'''}-H), 8.36 (2H, singlet, C_{5'''}-H), 8.38 (2H, singlet, C₃-H and C₅-H), 8.66 (1H, doublet of doublet, $J = 4.8 \text{ Hz}$ and 1.6 Hz , C_{6'''}-H), 8.82 (2H, singlet, C_{4'}-H and C_{4''}-H), 8.85 (1H, doublet, $J =$

0.8 Hz , C_{2'''}-H). ¹³C-APT (100 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 116.47(C), 119.39(C), 119.47(CH), 120.78(CH), 122.03(CH), 122.68(C), 123.59(C), 124.63(C), 125.33(CH), 127.25(C), 127.89(C), 128.58(CH), 128.89(C), 129.62(C), 132.34(C), 135.99(C), 139.53(CH), 141.64(CH), 142.72(C), 149.41(C), 149.49(C), 151.54(CH), 154.05(CH), 160.08(CO of coumarin). Anal. Calcd. for C₃₇H₂₂N₄O₄: C, 75.76; H, 3.78; N, 9.55 %. Found: C, 75.82; H, 3.85; N, 9.62 %.

8''-Methoxy-3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-3''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarin (6b): Yield: 73%, m.p. 230-232°C., IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}): 1728 (C=O stretching of δ -lactone of coumarin), 1612 and 1481 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 687 and 756 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 2978 (aliphatic C-H stretching), 3062 (aromatic C-H stretching). ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 4.02 (3H, singlet, OCH₃), 7.14-8.07 (14H, multiplet, Ar-H except C_{5'''}-H, C₃-H, C₅-H, C_{6'''}-H, C_{4'}-H, C_{4''}-H and C_{2'''}-H), 8.36 (2H, multiplet, C_{5'''}-H and C₃-H), 8.40 (1H, doublet, $J = 1.2 \text{ Hz}$, C₅-H), 8.64 (1H, doublet of doublet, $J = 4.8 \text{ Hz}$ and 1.6 Hz , C_{6'''}-H), 8.80 (1H, singlet, C_{4'}-H), 8.82 (1H, singlet, C_{4''}-H), 8.84 (1H, doublet, $J = 2.0 \text{ Hz}$, C_{2'''}-H). ¹³C-APT (100 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 56.23(OCH₃), 114.00(CH), 116.38(CH), 118.48(CH), 119.22(C), 119.74(CH), 120.04(CH), 120.28(C), 120.68(C), 122.56(CH), 123.59(CH), 124.43(CH), 124.59(CH), 124.90(C), 125.33(C), 127.20(CH), 127.89(CH), 128.25(CH), 128.93(C), 129.59(CH), 129.78(CH), 132.28(CH), 136.01(CH), 136.26(CH), 139.50(C), 141.56(C), 142.71(CH), 142.86(CH), 146.94(C), 148.01(C), 149.32(C), 149.60(C), 150.17(C), 151.38(C), 159.75(CO of coumarin), 160.05(CO of coumarin). Anal. Calcd. for C₃₈H₂₄N₄O₅: C, 74.02; H, 3.92; N, 9.09 %. Found: C, 74.11; H, 4.09; N, 9.16 %.

6''-Bromo-3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-3''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarin (6c): Yield: 68%, m.p. 145-147°C., IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}): 1720 (C=O stretching of δ -lactone of coumarin), 1620 and 1496 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 694 and 771 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 3055 (aromatic C-H stretching). ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 7.38-8.08 (14H, multiplet, Ar-H except C_{5'''}-H, C₃-H, C₅-H, C_{6'''}-H, C_{4'}-H, C_{4''}-H and C_{2'''}-H), 8.36 (1H, singlet, C_{5'''}-H), 8.37 (1H, doublet, $J = 1.6 \text{ Hz}$, C₃-H), 8.41 (1H, doublet, $J = 1.6 \text{ Hz}$, C₅-H), 8.65 (1H, doublet of

doublet, $J = 4.8$ Hz and 1.2 Hz, C₆'''-H), 8.76 (1H, singlet, C₄'-H), 8.81 (1H, singlet, C₄''-H), 8.83 (1H, doublet, $J = 1.6$ Hz, C₂'''-H). ¹³C-APT (100 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 110.09(C), 112.93(C), 115.65(C), 115.76(C), 117.14(CH), 118.06(C), 118.59(C), 118.70(CH), 118.82(CH), 119.31(C), 120.08(CH), 122.25(CH), 122.67(CH), 126.92(CH), 128.08(CH), 129.41(CH), 130.01(CH), 130.65(CH), 132.44(CH), 137.11(CH), 138.09(C), 139.28(CH), 140.65(CH), 141.08(CH), 143.62(C), 145.77(C), 146.26(CH), 146.65(CH), 146.82(C), 148.68(CH), 149.63(C), 152.91(C), 154.13(C), 160.72(CO of coumarin), 161.15(CO of coumarin). Anal.Calcd. for C₃₇H₂₁BrN₄O₄: C, 66.78; H, 3.18; N, 8.42 %. Found: C, 66.82; H, 3.22; N, 8.49 %.

8'-Methoxy-3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-3'''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4'''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarin

(6d): Yield: 73%., m.p.230-232°C., IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹): 1728 (C=O stretching of δ -lactone of coumarin), 1612 and 1481 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 687 and 756 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 2978 (aliphatic C-H stretching), 3062 (aromatic C-H stretching). ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 4.12 (3H, singlet, OCH₃), 7.15-8.06 (14H, multiplet, Ar-H except C₅'''-H, C₃-H, C₅-H, C₆'''-H, C₄'-H, C₄''-H and C₂'''-H), 8.36 (2H, multiplet, C₅'''-H and C₃-H), 8.40 (1H, doublet, $J = 1.2$ Hz, C₅-H), 8.64 (1H, doublet of doublet, $J = 4.0$ Hz and 1.6 Hz, C₆'''-H), 8.81 (1H, singlet, C₄'-H), 8.82 (1H, singlet, C₄''-H), 8.85 (1H, doublet, $J = 2.0$ Hz, C₂'''-H). ¹³C-APT (100 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 56.28(OCH₃), 114.05(CH), 116.43(CH), 118.58(CH), 119.20(C), 119.78(CH), 120.04(C), 120.24(CH), 120.66(C), 122.58(CH), 123.59(CH), 124.40(CH), 124.50(CH), 124.93(C), 125.33(C), 127.29(CH), 127.89(CH), 128.23(CH), 128.95(C), 129.59(CH), 129.76(CH), 132.28(CH), 136.00(CH), 136.26(CH), 139.51(C), 141.56(C), 142.71(CH), 142.86(CH), 146.98(C), 148.02(C), 149.30(C), 149.65(C), 150.17(C), 151.34(C), 159.70(CO of coumarin), 160.05(CO of coumarin). Anal.Calcd. for C₃₈H₂₄N₄O₅: C, 74.02; H, 3.92; N, 9.09 %. Found: C, 74.11; H, 4.09; N, 9.16 %.

8',8''-Dimethoxy-3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-3'''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4'''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarin

(6e): Yield: 78%., m.p.290-292°C., IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹): 1712 (C=O stretching of δ -lactone of coumarin), 1620 and 1496 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 663 and 748 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 2970

(aliphatic C-H stretching), 3055 (aromatic C-H stretching). ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 4.00 (6H, singlet, 2 x OCH₃), 7.11-8.03 (13H, multiplet, Ar-H except C₅'''-H, C₃-H, C₅-H, C₆'''-H, C₄'-H, C₄''-H and C₂'''-H), 8.34 (1H, singlet, C₅'''-H), 8.37 (2H, singlet, C₃-H and C₅-H), 8.61 (1H, doublet of doublet, $J = 4.8$ Hz and 1.6 Hz, C₆'''-H), 8.79 (2H, singlet, C₄'-H and C₄''-H), 8.81 (1H, doublet, $J = 2.0$ Hz, and C₂'''-H). ¹³C-APT (100 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 56.21(OCH₃), 114.07(CH), 119.50(CH), 120.14(C), 120.39(CH), 120.77(C), 122.72(CH), 123.67(CH), 124.56(CH), 125.50(C), 127.27(CH), 128.03(CH), 128.66(C), 129.67(CH), 135.99(CH), 139.65(C), 141.67(C), 142.94(CH), 143.63(C), 146.98(C), 149.51(CH), 151.53(C), 159.61(CO of coumarin). Anal.Calcd. for C₃₉H₂₆N₄O₆: C, 72.44; H, 4.05; N, 8.66 %. Found: C, 72.59; H, 4.15; N, 8.71 %.

6''-Bromo-8'-methoxy-3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-3'''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4'''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarin

(6f): Yield: 70%., m.p.200-202°C., IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹): 1728 (C=O stretching of δ -lactone of coumarin), 1620 and 1481 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 679 and 779 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 2985 (aliphatic C-H stretching), 3047 (aromatic C-H stretching). ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 4.00 (3H, singlet, OCH₃), 7.13-8.08 (13H, multiplet, Ar-H except C₅'''-H, C₃-H, C₅-H, C₆'''-H, C₄'-H, C₄''-H and C₂'''-H), 8.34 (2H, multiplet, C₅'''-H and C₃-H), 8.41 (1H, poorly resolved doublet, C₅-H), 8.64 (1H, poorly resolved doublet of doublet, C₆'''-H), 8.76 (1H, singlet, C₄'-H), 8.78 (1H, singlet, C₄''-H), 8.82 (1H, poorly resolved doublet, C₂'''-H). ¹³C-APT (100 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 56.22(OCH₃), 114.11(CH), 115.79(C), 117.17(CH), 118.06(CH), 119.34(C), 119.99(CH), 120.28(C), 120.53(CH), 120.92(CH), 122.50(CH), 122.80(CH), 123.64(CH), 124.43(CH), 125.17(C), 126.06(C), 127.29(CH), 127.88(CH), 129.66(CH), 131.04(CH), 131.83(C), 134.99(CH), 136.13(CH), 139.48(C), 141.31(CH), 141.70(C), 142.94(CH), 144.76(C), 145.90(C), 146.64(C), 146.93(C), 149.35(C), 150.64(C), 151.52(C), 160.06(CO of coumarin), 161.64(CO of coumarin). Anal.Calcd. for C₃₈H₂₃BrN₄O₅: C, 65.62; H, 3.33; N, 8.06 %. Found: C, 65.70; H, 3.37; N, 8.13 %.

6''-Bromo-3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-3'''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4'''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarin

(6g): Yield: 68%., m.p.145-147°C., IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹): 1720 (C=O stretching of δ -lactone of coumarin),

1620 and 1496 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 694 and 771 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 3055 (aromatic C-H stretching). ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 7.38-8.08 (14H, multiplet, Ar-H except C_{5'''}-H, C₃-H, C₅-H, C_{6'''}-H, C_{4'}-H, C_{4''}-H and C_{2'''}-H), 8.36 (1H, singlet, C_{5'''}-H), 8.37 (1H, doublet, *J* = 1.6 Hz, C₃-H), 8.41 (1H, doublet, *J* = 1.6 Hz, C₅-H), 8.65 (1H, doublet of doublet, *J* = 4.4 Hz and 1.6 Hz, C_{6'''}-H), 8.76 (1H, singlet, C_{4'}-H), 8.80 (1H, singlet, C_{4''}-H), 8.83 (1H, doublet, *J* = 1.2 Hz, C_{2'''}-H). ¹³C-APT (100 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 109.99(C), 112.95(C), 115.63(C), 115.83(CH), 117.13(CH), 118.08(CH), 118.59(C), 118.71(C), 118.82(CH), 119.31(C), 120.08(CH), 122.25(C), 122.63(CH), 126.92(CH), 128.01(CH), 129.44(CH), 130.15(CH), 130.56(CH), 132.41(CH), 137.06(CH), 138.18(C), 139.29(CH), 140.65(CH), 141.08(CH), 143.62(C), 145.72(C), 146.26(CH), 146.65(CH), 146.76(C), 148.68(CH), 149.67(C), 152.90(C), 154.14(C), 160.77(CO of coumarin), 161.11(CO of coumarin). Anal. Calcd. for C₃₇H₂₁BrN₄O₄: C, 66.78; H, 3.18; N, 8.42 %. Found: C, 66.82; H, 3.22; N, 8.49 %.

6'-Bromo-8''-methoxy-3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-3''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarin (6h): Yield: 70%., m.p.200-202°C., IR (KBr, ν_{max}, cm⁻¹): 1728 (C=O stretching of δ-lactone of coumarin), 1620 and 1481 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 679 and 779 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 2985 (aliphatic C-H stretching), 3047 (aromatic C-H stretching). ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 4.10 (3H, singlet, OCH₃), 7.13-8.08 (13H, multiplet, Ar-H except C_{5'''}-H, C₃-H, C₅-H, C_{6'''}-H, C_{4'}-H, C_{4''}-H and C_{2'''}-H), 8.35 (2H, multiplet, C_{5'''}-H and C₃-H), 8.41 (1H, poorly resolved doublet, C₅-H), 8.63 (1H, poorly resolved doublet of doublet, C_{6'''}-H), 8.76 (1H, singlet, C_{4'}-H), 8.78 (1H, singlet, C_{4''}-H), 8.83 (1H, poorly resolved doublet, C_{2'''}-H). ¹³C-APT (100 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 56.28(OCH₃), 114.92(CH), 115.79(C), 117.13(CH), 118.11(CH), 119.31(C), 119.90(CH), 120.22(C), 120.57(CH), 120.89(CH), 122.59(CH), 122.80(CH), 123.64(CH), 124.34(CH), 125.13(C), 126.11(C), 127.29(CH), 127.89(CH), 129.69(CH), 131.11(CH), 131.92(C), 134.90(CH), 136.17(CH), 139.43(C), 141.28(CH), 141.76(C), 142.99(CH), 144.70(C), 145.93(C), 146.69(C), 146.99(C), 149.43(C), 150.69(C), 151.59(C), 160.11(CO of coumarin), 161.66(CO of coumarin). Anal. Calcd. for C₃₈H₂₃BrN₄O₅: C, 65.62;

H, 3.33; N, 8.06 %. Found: C, 65.70; H, 3.37; N, 8.13 %.

6',6''-Dibromo-3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-3''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarin (6i): Yield: 65%., m.p.134-136°C., IR (KBr, ν_{max}, cm⁻¹): 1728 (C=O stretching of δ-lactone of coumarin), 1620 and 1481 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 678 and 779 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 3070 (aromatic C-H stretching). ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 7.35-8.07 (13H, multiplet, Ar-H except C_{5'''}-H, C₃-H, C₅-H, C_{6'''}-H, C_{4'}-H, C_{4''}-H and C_{2'''}-H), 8.36 (1H, singlet, C_{5'''}-H), 8.37 (2H, singlet, C₃-H and C₅-H), 8.65 (1H, doublet of doublet, *J* = 4.8 Hz and 1.6 Hz, C_{6'''}-H), 8.82 (2H, singlet, C_{4'}-H and C_{4''}-H), 8.84 (1H, poorly resolved doublet, C_{2'''}-H). ¹³C-APT (100 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 119.30(CH), 119.53(CH), 124.60(CH), 124.90(C), 125.24(C), 125.46(CH), 125.58(CH), 126.91(CH), 127.79(CH), 129.67(CH), 130.77(C), 133.20(CH), 134.19(CH), 136.07(CH), 143.91(C), 145.35(C), 146.79(CH), 147.34(CH), 149.33(C), 151.31(C), 156.06(C), 157.28(C), 158.27(C), 160.31(CO of coumarin). Anal. Calcd. for C₃₇H₂₀Br₂N₄O₄: C, 59.70; H, 2.71; N, 7.53 %. Found: C, 59.76; H, 2.77; N, 7.59 %.

3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-4''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarin (7a): Yield: 78%., m.p.293-295°C., IR (KBr, ν_{max}, cm⁻¹): 1736 (C=O stretching of δ-lactone of coumarin), 1627 and 1488 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 679 and 756 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 3062 (aromatic C-H stretching). ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 7.28-7.86 (15H, multiplet, Ar-H except C_{5'''}-H, C₃-H, C₅-H, C_{2'''}-H, C_{6'''}-H, C_{4'}-H and C_{4''}-H), 8.30 (1H, singlet, C_{5'''}-H), 8.37 (2H, singlet, C₃-H and C₅-H), 8.64 (2H, doublet, *J* = 6.0 Hz, C_{2'''}-H and C_{6'''}-H), 8.82 (2H, singlet, C_{4'}-H and C_{4''}-H). ¹³C-APT (100 MHz, CDCl₃, δ): 116.50(CH), 119.40(CH), 121.11(C), 122.92(CH), 122.96(CH), 123.68(CH), 124.68(CH), 125.20(C), 127.46(CH), 128.32(CH), 128.91(CH), 129.65(C), 132.43(CH), 139.38(C), 140.68(C), 141.46(C), 142.85(CH), 147.94(C), 149.54(CH), 151.58(C), 154.00(C), 160.13(CO of coumarin). Anal. Calcd. for C₃₇H₂₂N₄O₄: C, 75.76; H, 3.78; N, 9.55 %. Found: C, 75.82; H, 3.85; N, 9.62 %.

8''-Methoxy-3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-4''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarin

(7b): Yield: 74%, m.p.282-284°C., IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}): 1728 (C=O stretching of δ -lactone of coumarin), 1612 and 1473 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 686 and 756 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 2977 (aliphatic C-H stretching), 3055 (aromatic C-H stretching). $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ): 4.03 (3H, singlet, OCH_3), 7.13-7.86 (14H, multiplet, Ar-H except C_5''' -H, C_3 -H, C_5 -H, C_2''' -H, C_6''' -H, C_4' -H and C_4'' -H), 8.30 (1H, singlet, C_5''' -H), 8.35 (1H, doublet, $J = 1.2 \text{ Hz}$, C_3 -H), 8.39 (1H, doublet, $J = 2.0 \text{ Hz}$, C_5 -H), 8.63 (2H, doublet, $J = 6.0 \text{ Hz}$, C_2''' -H and C_6''' -H), 8.81 (1H, singlet, C_4' -H), 8.82 (1H, singlet, C_4'' -H). $^{13}\text{C-APT}$ (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ): 56.24(OCH_3), 114.06(CH), 116.43(CH), 119.34(C), 119.38(CH), 119.44(C), 120.00(CH), 120.27(C), 121.04(CH), 122.84(CH), 122.96(CH), 124.50(CH), 124.65(CH), 125.09(C), 125.25(C), 127.42(CH), 128.32(CH), 128.94(CH), 129.62(CH), 132.38(CH), 139.37(C), 140.68(C), 141.40(C), 142.85(CH), 143.00(CH), 143.61(C), 146.94(C), 147.90(C), 149.51(CH), 151.45(C), 151.48(C), 153.95(C), 159.58(CO of coumarin), 160.11(CO of coumarin). Anal.Calcd. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5$: C, 74.02; H, 3.92; N, 9.09 %. Found: C, 74.11; H, 4.09; N, 9.16 %.

6''-Bromo-3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-4''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl) dicoumarin

(7c): Yield: 69%, m.p.170-172°C., IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}): 1712 (C=O stretching of δ -lactone of coumarin), 1627 and 1488 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 679 and 779 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 3061 (aromatic C-H stretching). $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ): 7.36-7.88 (14H, multiplet, Ar-H except C_5''' -H, C_3 -H, C_5 -H, C_2''' -H, C_6''' -H, C_4' -H and C_4'' -H), 8.31 (1H, singlet, C_5''' -H), 8.37 (1H, doublet, $J = 1.6 \text{ Hz}$, C_3 -H), 8.41 (1H, doublet, $J = 1.6 \text{ Hz}$, C_5 -H), 8.64 (2H, doublet, $J = 6.4 \text{ Hz}$, C_2''' -H and C_6''' -H), 8.76 (1H, singlet, C_4' -H), 8.81 (1H, singlet, C_4'' -H). $^{13}\text{C-APT}$ (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ): 112.43(C), 114.44(CH), 115.96(CH), 117.22(CH), 118.03(C), 119.54(CH), 120.48(CH), 121.96(C), 122.99(CH), 123.73(CH), 126.02(CH), 127.16(CH), 127.72(C), 127.86(CH), 127.99(CH), 129.48(CH), 129.72(CH), 130.58(CH), 133.26(CH), 135.23(C), 139.07(C), 139.56(C), 140.08(C), 143.85(C), 146.10(C), 148.61(C), 150.15(CH), 150.66(C), 152.64(C), 154.71(C), 161.79(CO of coumarin), 162.03(CO of coumarin). Anal.Calcd. for

$\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{21}\text{BrN}_4\text{O}_4$: C, 66.78; H, 3.18; N, 8.42 %. Found: C, 66.82; H, 3.24; N, 8.50 %.

8''-Methoxy-3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-4''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarin

(7d): Yield: 74%, m.p.282°C., IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}): 1728 (C=O stretching of δ -lactone of coumarin), 1612 and 1473 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 686 and 756 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 2977 (aliphatic C-H stretching), 3055 (aromatic C-H stretching). $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ): 4.02 (3H, singlet, OCH_3), 7.15-7.87 (14H, multiplet, Ar-H except C_5''' -H, C_3 -H, C_5 -H, C_2''' -H, C_6''' -H, C_4' -H and C_4'' -H), 8.31 (1H, singlet, C_5''' -H), 8.37 (1H, doublet, $J = 1.2 \text{ Hz}$, C_3 -H), 8.41 (1H, doublet, $J = 1.2 \text{ Hz}$, C_5 -H), 8.64 (2H, doublet, $J = 5.2 \text{ Hz}$, C_2''' -H and C_6''' -H), 8.81 (1H, singlet, C_4' -H), 8.82 (1H, singlet, C_4'' -H). $^{13}\text{C-APT}$ (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ): 56.28(OCH_3), 114.09(CH), 116.50(CH), 119.32(C), 119.34(CH), 119.43(C), 120.04(CH), 120.25(C), 121.00(CH), 122.86(CH), 122.94(CH), 124.48(CH), 124.62(CH), 125.06(C), 125.27(C), 127.43(CH), 128.37(CH), 128.94(CH), 129.65(CH), 132.42(CH), 139.40(C), 140.62(C), 141.37(C), 142.90(CH), 143.00(CH), 143.68(C), 146.96(C), 147.85(C), 149.51(CH), 151.45(C), 151.50(C), 153.96(C), 159.61(CO of coumarin), 160.14(CO of coumarin). Anal.Calcd. for $\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{O}_5$: C, 74.02; H, 3.92; N, 9.09 %. Found: C, 74.11; H, 4.09; N, 9.16 %.

8'',8''-Dimethoxy-3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-4''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarin

(7e): Yield: 76%, m.p.296-298°C., IR (KBr, ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}): 1720 (C=O stretching of δ -lactone of coumarin), 1627 and 1496 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 687 and 779 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 2985 (aliphatic C-H stretching), 3070 (aromatic C-H stretching). $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ): 3.99 (6H, singlet, 2 x OCH_3), 7.13-7.84 (13H, multiplet, Ar-H except C_5''' -H, C_3 -H, C_5 -H, C_2''' -H, C_6''' -H, C_4' -H and C_4'' -H), 8.30 (1H, singlet, C_5''' -H), 8.37 (2H, singlet, C_3 -H and C_5 -H), 8.60 (2H, poorly resolved doublet, C_2''' -H and C_6''' -H), 8.79 (2H, singlet, C_4' -H and C_4'' -H). $^{13}\text{C-APT}$ (100 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ): 56.61(OCH_3), 110.26(C), 113.13(C), 114.24(C), 114.52(CH), 116.00(C), 118.77(CH), 120.07(CH), 121.73(CH), 122.84(CH), 123.92(CH), 125.34(CH), 126.91(CH), 129.41(CH), 130.06(CH), 138.15(C), 140.11(CH), 143.65(C), 144.30(C), 146.98(C), 148.83(C), 149.94(C), 160.86(CO of coumarin).

Anal.Calcd. for $C_{39}H_{26}N_4O_6$: C, 72.44; H, 4.05; N, 8.66 %. Found: C, 72.59; H, 4.15; N, 8.71 %.

6''-Bromo-8'-methoxy-3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-4''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarin (7f):Yield: 72%., m.p.148-150°C., IR (KBr, ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 1735 (C=O stretching of δ -lactone of coumarin), 1628 and 1458 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 678 and 786 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 2970 (aliphatic C-H stretching), 3063 (aromatic C-H stretching). 1H -NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$, δ): 3.99 (3H, singlet, OCH_3), 7.11-7.86 (13H, multiplet, Ar-H except C_5''' -H, C_3 -H, C_5 -H, C_2'''' -H, C_6'''' -H, C_4' -H and C_4'' -H), 8.30 (1H, singlet, C_5''' -H), 8.34 (1H, poorly resolved doublet, C_3 -H), 8.38 (1H, poorly resolved doublet, C_5 -H), 8.62 (2H, doublet, $J = 6.0$ Hz, C_2'''' -H and C_6'''' -H), 8.80 (1H, singlet, C_4' -H), 8.81 (1H, singlet, C_4'' -H). ^{13}C -APT (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$, δ):56.28(OCH_3), 114.11(CH), 116.46(CH), 119.41(C), 119.46(CH), 120.03(C), 120.27(CH), 121.07(C), 122.92(CH), 124.49(CH), 124.64(CH), 125.19(C), 125.35(C), 127.41(CH), 128.31(CH), 128.92(CH), 129.62(CH), 132.38(CH), 139.41(C), 140.55(C), 141.47(C), 142.81(CH), 142.97(CH), 143.68(C), 147.00(C), 148.00(C), 149.68(CH), 151.50(C), 151.53(C), 153.99(C), 159.56(CO of coumarin), 160.09(CO of coumarin).Anal.Calcd. for $C_{38}H_{23}BrN_4O_5$: C, 65.62; H, 3.33; N, 8.06 %. Found: C, 65.67; H, 3.40; N, 8.13 %.

6'-Bromo-3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-4''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarin (7g):Yield: 69%., m.p.170-172°C., IR (KBr, ν_{max} , cm^{-1}):1712 (C=O stretching of δ -lactone of coumarin), 1620 and 1488 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 679 and 779 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 3061 (aromatic C-H stretching). 1H -NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$, δ): 7.36-7.88 (14H, multiplet, Ar-H except C_5''' -H, C_3 -H, C_5 -H, C_2'''' -H, C_6'''' -H, C_4' -H and C_4'' -H), 8.32 (1H, singlet, C_5''' -H), 8.36 (1H, doublet, $J = 2.0$ Hz, C_3 -H), 8.41 (1H, doublet, $J = 2.0$ Hz, C_5 -H), 8.64 (2H, doublet, $J = 6.4$ Hz, C_2'''' -H and C_6'''' -H), 8.76 (1H, singlet, C_4' -H), 8.81 (1H, singlet, C_4'' -H). ^{13}C -APT (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$, δ):112.48(C), 114.48(CH), 115.99(CH), 117.22(CH), 118.07(C), 119.58(CH), 120.43(CH), 121.99(C), 122.96(CH), 123.79(CH), 126.08(CH), 127.16(CH), 127.71(C), 127.86(CH), 127.96(CH), 129.43(CH), 129.71(CH), 130.54(CH), 133.26(CH), 135.23(C), 139.03(C), 139.54(C), 140.02(C), 143.86(C), 146.10(C), 148.64(C), 150.15(CH),

150.66(C), 152.61(C), 154.79(C), 161.73(CO of coumarin),162.13(CO of coumarin).Anal.Calcd. for $C_{37}H_{21}BrN_4O_4$: C, 66.78; H, 3.18; N, 8.42 %. Found: C, 66.82; H, 3.24; N, 8.50 %.

6'-Bromo-8''-methoxy-3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-4''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarin (7h):Yield: 72%., m.p.148-150°C., IR (KBr, ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 1735 (C=O stretching of δ -lactone of coumarin), 1628 and 1458 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 678 and 786 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 2970 (aliphatic C-H stretching), 3063 (aromatic C-H stretching). 1H -NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$, δ): 4.00 (3H, singlet, OCH_3), 7.12-7.86 (13H, multiplet, Ar-H except C_5''' -H, C_3 -H, C_5 -H, C_2'''' -H, C_6'''' -H, C_4' -H and C_4'' -H), 8.30 (1H, singlet, C_5''' -H), 8.34 (1H, poorly resolved doublet, C_3 -H), 8.38 (1H, poorly resolved doublet, C_5 -H), 8.62 (2H, doublet, $J = 5.6$ Hz, C_2'''' -H and C_6'''' -H), 8.80 (1H, singlet, C_4' -H), 8.82 (1H, singlet, C_4'' -H). ^{13}C -APT (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$, δ):56.32(OCH_3), 114.13(CH), 116.41(CH), 119.41(C), 119.46(CH), 120.03(C), 120.28(CH), 121.03(C), 122.99(CH), 124.50(CH), 124.68(CH), 125.19(C), 125.35(C), 127.41(CH), 128.33(CH), 128.97(CH), 129.62(CH), 132.33(CH), 139.47(C), 140.56(C), 141.41(C), 142.80(CH), 142.92(CH), 143.68(C), 147.04(C), 148.02(C), 149.64(CH), 151.50(C), 151.53(C), 153.92(C), 159.55(CO of coumarin), 160.08(CO of coumarin). Anal.Calcd. for $C_{38}H_{23}BrN_4O_5$: C, 65.62; H, 3.33; N, 8.06 %. Found: C, 65.67; H, 3.40; N, 8.13 %.

6',6''-Dibromo-3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-4''''-yl)-1H-pyrazol-4''''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarin (7i):Yield: 66%., m.p.142°C., IR (KBr, ν_{max} , cm^{-1}): 1728 (C=O stretching of δ -lactone of coumarin), 1627 and 1488 (aromatic C=C and C=N stretchings), 687 and 756 (C-H bending vibrations of mono substituted benzene ring), 3070 (aromatic C-H stretching). 1H -NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$, δ): 7.34-7.84 (13H, multiplet, Ar-H except C_5''' -H, C_3 -H, C_5 -H, C_2'''' -H, C_6'''' -H, C_4' -H and C_4'' -H), 8.30 (1H, singlet, C_5''' -H), 8.36 (2H, singlet, C_3 -H and C_5 -H), 8.62 (2H, doublet, $J = 4.8$ Hz, C_2'''' -H and C_6'''' -H), 8.81 (2H, singlet, C_4' -H and C_4'' -H). ^{13}C -APT (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$, δ):111.79(C), 117.88(C), 119.25(CH), 119.55(CH), 121.43(C), 122.28(CH), 123.05(CH), 123.76(C), 125.60(CH), 127.23(CH), 127.97(CH), 129.74(CH), 130.07(C), 130.77(CH), 133.03(CH), 133.69(CH), 139.05(C), 140.15(C), 150.05(C), 150.72(C), 154.04(C), 161.06(CO of

coumarin). Anal. Calcd. for $C_{37}H_{20}Br_2N_4O_4$: C, 59.70; H, 2.71; N, 7.53 %. Found: C, 59.76; H, 2.77; N, 7.59 %.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Chemistry

In the present work the synthesis of various 3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-3'''-yl)-1*H*-pyrazol-4'''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarins (**6a-i**) and 3',3''-(4-(1'''-phenyl-3'''-(pyridin-4'''-yl)-1*H*-pyrazol-4'''-yl)pyridine-2,6-diyl)dicoumarins (**7a-i**) has been carried out by the reaction of appropriate 3-coumarinoyl methyl pyridinium bromide salt (**3a-c**) with coumarin chalcones 3-(3-(1-phenyl-3-(pyridin-3-yl)-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)acryloyl)coumarins (**4a-c**) and 3-(3-(1-phenyl-3-(pyridin-4-yl)-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)acryloyl)coumarins (**5a-c**) respectively in the presence of ammonium acetate in refluxing acetic acid proceeded smoothly and gave the compound **6a** as a yellow solid product in 71% yield. The structures of all synthesized compounds (**6a-i**) and (**7a-i**) were established by IR, 1H -NMR, ^{13}C -APT and selected mass spectral data are shown in experimental section.

BIOLOGICAL EVALUATION

Antimicrobial activity

The newly synthesized target compounds (**6a-i**) and (**7a-i**) were evaluated for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against two Gram positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC 96) and *Bacillus subtilis* (MTCC 441) and two Gram negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* (MTCC 443) and *Salmonella typhi* (MTCC 98). They were also evaluated for their *in vitro* antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* (MTCC 227) and *Aspergillus niger* (MTCC 282) as fungal strains. Broth dilution method was used for the determination of the antibacterial and antifungal activity as recommended by NCCLS³³. Ampicillin, Chloramphenicol, Ciprofloxacin, Norfloxacin and Gentamycin were used as standard antibacterial drugs, whereas Griseofulvin and Nystatin were used as standard antifungal drugs. All MTCC cultures were collected from Institute of Microbial Technology, Chandigarh and tested against above mentioned known drugs. Mueller-Hinton broth was used as the nutrient medium for the test bacteria and Sabouraud Dextrose broth was used for the test fungi. Inoculum size for the test strains was adjusted to 10⁸ CFU (Colony Forming Unit per millilitre) per millilitre by comparing the turbidity. Each synthesized compound was diluted with DMSO so as to have the stock solution of 2000 μ g/mL

concentration as a stock solution. The results were recorded in the form of primary and secondary screening. The synthesized compounds (**6a-i**) and (**7a-i**) were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity at the concentration of 1000, 500 and 250 μ g/mL for the primary screening. The synthesized compound showing activity against microbes in the primary screening were further screened in a second set of dilution at concentrations of 200, 100, 62.5, 50 and 25 μ g/mL. The suspension of 10 μ L from each well were further incubated and growth was noted at 37°C after 24 hour for bacteria and 48 hour for fungi. The lowest concentration which showed no visible growth (turbidity) after spot subculture was considered as the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for each compound.

The investigation of the data summarized in (Table-1) reveals that many compounds were found to be active against Gram-positive bacteria while some of the compounds were found to be active against Gram-negative bacterial and fungal species as compared to that of the standard antimicrobial drugs.

Antimicrobial results

The compounds (**6a-i**) and (**7a-i**) were screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial and antifungal evaluation against various bacterial and fungal pathogens by broth dilution method. Ampicillin, Chloramphenicol, Norfloxacin, Ciprofloxacin, Gentamycin, Griseofulvin and Nystatin were used as standard drugs. The values of MIC are summarized in Table-1.

Upon evaluating the antimicrobial activity data, it has been observed that compound **7e** and **7f** (MIC=62.5 μ g/mL) showed excellent activity compared to Ampicillin (MIC=250 μ g/mL) and Norfloxacin (MIC=100 μ g/mL) against gram positive bacteria *Bacillus subtilis*. Compounds **6b**, **6f**, **7a** and **7i** (MIC=100 μ g/mL) exhibited excellent activity against gram positive bacteria *Bacillus subtilis* compared to Ampicillin (MIC=250 μ g/mL) and equipotent to Norfloxacin (MIC=100 μ g/mL). Compounds **6a**, **6c**, **6d** and **7d** (MIC=125 μ g/mL) exhibited excellent activity compared to Ampicillin (MIC=250 μ g/mL) against gram positive bacteria *Bacillus subtilis*. Compounds **6g**, **6h**, **7c** and **7h** (MIC=200 μ g/mL) showed good activity against gram positive bacteria *Bacillus subtilis* compared to Ampicillin (MIC=250 μ g/mL). Compounds **6e**, **6i**, **7b** and **7g** (MIC=250 μ g/mL) were found comparable to Ampicillin (MIC=250 μ g/mL) against gram positive bacteria *Bacillus subtilis*. Compounds **6f**

(MIC=50µg/mL), **7a** (MIC=62.5µg/mL), compounds **6b**, **6d**, **6g**, **7b**, **7d**, **7f** (MIC=100µg/mL) and compounds **6c**, **6e**, **6h**, **7e**, **7h** and **7i** (MIC=125µg/mL) showed excellent activity against gram positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* compared to Ampicillin (MIC= 250µg/mL). Compounds **6i**, **7c** and **7g** (MIC=200µg/mL) showed good activity against gram positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* compared to Ampicillin (MIC=250µg/mL). Compounds **6g**, **7c** and **7i** (MIC=62.5µg/mL) have shown excellent activity against *Escherichia coli* compared to Ampicillin (MIC=100µg/mL). Compounds **6c**, **6d**, **7f** and **7g** (MIC=100µg/mL) showed equipotent activity to Ampicillin (MIC= 100µg/mL) against gram negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*. Compounds **7h** (MIC= 50µg/mL) exhibited excellent activity against *Salmonella typhi* compared to Ampicillin (MIC=100µg/mL) and equipotent to Chloramphenicol (MIC=50µg/mL). Compounds **6c** and **6h** (MIC=62.5µg/mL) showed excellent activity against *Salmonella typhi* compared to Ampicillin (MIC=100µg/mL). Compounds **6b**, **6f**, **6g**, **6i**, **7a**, **7b**, **7c**, **7e**, **7f** and **7i** (MIC=100µg/mL) were found equipotent to Ampicillin (MIC = 100µg/mL) against gram negative bacteria *Salmonella typhi*. Compounds **6d** (MIC=200µg/mL), compounds **6a** and **7c**

(MIC=250µg/mL) were found to be more active than Griseofulvin (MIC=500µg/mL) against fungal pathogen *Candida albicans* while compounds **6b**, **7b**, **7e** and **7g** were found equipotent to Griseofulvin (MIC= 500µg/mL) against *Candida albicans*. None of the tested compounds showed better activity against *Aspergillusnigerfungi*. Upon examining the antimicrobial data it is apparent that almost all the compounds **6a-i** and **7a-i** exhibited excellent activity against gram-positive bacteria *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus* as compared to Ampicillin. Examining the antimicrobial data from the table, it has been observed that the derivatization of the parent molecule altered the antimicrobial potency of the synthesized analogs. The observation indicates that varying the substitution on coumarin ring i.e. R, R₂ = OCH₃ and R₁, R₃ = Br affect the antibacterial activity to a remarkable extent. When OCH₃ group present as a substituent on coumarin ring increased the antimicrobial activity against *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, while introducing of Br group in coumarin nucleus the antibacterial potency enhanced markedly.

Among all the tested compounds, the compounds **6c**, **6g**, **6h**, **7c**, **7f**, **7h** and **7i** were found to be the most proficient members of the series.

Table-1 Antimicrobial activity of compounds (6a-i) and (7a-i)

Compound	Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC, $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)					
	Gram +ve bacteria		Gram -ve bacteria		Fungi	
	<i>B.s.</i>	<i>S.a.</i>	<i>E.c.</i>	<i>S.t.</i>	<i>A.n.</i>	<i>C.a.</i>
6a	125	250	125	200	500	250
6b	100	100	200	100	1000	500
6c	125	125	100	62.5	500	1000
6d	125	100	100	200	>1000	200
6e	250	125	125	250	200	1000
6f	100	50	200	100	>1000	>1000
6g	200	100	62.5	100	>1000	1000
6h	200	125	250	62.5	500	>1000
6i	250	200	200	100	500	>1000
7a	100	62.5	250	100	1000	>1000
7b	250	100	125	100	>1000	500
7c	200	200	62.5	100	500	250
7d	125	100	200	250	1000	>1000
7e	62.5	125	250	100	1000	500
7f	62.5	100	100	100	1000	1000
7g	250	200	100	125	1000	500
7h	200	125	125	50	>1000	1000
7i	100	125	62.5	100	500	1000
Ampicillin	250	250	100	100	-	-
Chloramphenicol	50	50	50	50	-	-
Ciprofloxacin	50	50	25	25	-	-
Norfloxacin	100	10	10	10	-	-
Gentamycin	1	0.25	0.05	5	-	-
Griseofulvin	-	-	-	-	100	500
Nystatin	-	-	-	-	100	100

B.s.: *Bacillus subtilis*, *S.a.:* *Staphylococcus aureus*, *E.c.:* *Escherichia coli*,
S.t.: *Salmonella typhi*, *A.n.:* *Aspergillus niger*, *C.a.:* *Candida albicans*

Compound	Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC, $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)					
	Gram +ve bacteria		Gram -ve bacteria		Fungi	
	<i>B.s.</i>	<i>S.a.</i>	<i>E.c.</i>	<i>S.t.</i>	<i>A.n.</i>	<i>C.a.</i>
6a	125	250	125	200	500	250
6b	100	100	200	100	1000	500
6c	125	125	100	62.5	500	1000
6d	125	100	100	200	>1000	200
6e	250	125	125	250	200	1000
6f	100	50	200	100	>1000	>1000
6g	200	100	62.5	100	>1000	1000
6h	200	125	250	62.5	500	>1000
6i	250	200	200	100	500	>1000
7a	100	62.5	250	100	1000	>1000
7b	250	100	125	100	>1000	500
7c	200	200	62.5	100	500	250
7d	125	100	200	250	1000	>1000
7e	62.5	125	250	100	1000	500
7f	62.5	100	100	100	1000	1000
7g	250	200	100	125	1000	500
7h	200	125	125	50	>1000	1000
7i	100	125	62.5	100	500	1000
Ampicillin	250	250	100	100	-	-
Chloramphenicol	50	50	50	50	-	-
Ciprofloxacin	50	50	25	25	-	-
Norfloxacin	100	10	10	10	-	-
Gentamycin	1	0.25	0.05	5	-	-
Griseofulvin	-	-	-	-	100	500
Nystatin	-	-	-	-	100	100

B.s.: *Bacillus subtilis*, *S.a.:* *Staphylococcus aureus*, *E.c.:* *Escherichia coli*,
S.t.: *Salmonella typhi*, *A.n.:* *Aspergillus niger*, *C.a.:* *Candida albicans*

CONCLUSION

A simple and convenient methodology has been developed for synthesis for a series of pyrazolylpyridyl substituted dicoumarins was described and the synthesized compounds were screened for their *in vitro* antimicrobial evaluation. The results indicated that all the synthesized compounds shown good antibacterial activity against bacterial and fungal pathogens as compared to standard drugs and emerged as potential lead compounds for further investigations.

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